

STATUS OF SOCIAL MOTIVES PERCEIVED BY THE SECONDARY SCHOOL TEACHERS OF WEST BENGAL

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ABSTRACT

Social motives are one of the crucial characteristics of a person. These are especially learned motives and their strength differs from one individual to other. There are four dimensions of this social motives namely, Achievement Motives, Power Motives, Affiliation Motives, Approval Motives. This study tried to find out the status of social motives among secondary school teachers of West Bengal. The study was conducted upon 382 secondary school teachers. The Social Motive Scale (SMS), by Dr. Singh and Dr. Pandey (2010) were used in the study. It was typically a survey based study. The results showed that both Power Motives and Approval Motives of Social Motives followed normal trends where Achievement Motives and Affiliation Motives of Social Motives followed positively skewed and negatively skewed trends respectively. But the status of secondary school teachers regarding Social Motives collectively followed normal trends.

KEYWORDS

Social Motives, Secondary School Teachers, Achievement Motives, Power Motives, Affiliation Motives, Approval Motives

INTRODUCTION

A teacher is coming from different social background and from those societal contexts they perceive many habits, motives and behavior that may affect their daily classroom teaching or in overall his teaching profession. Social motives are also like that which can be acquired or learned from the society only. Under the purview of social motives there are also some other constructs or dimensions like need for achievement, need for power, need for affiliation or need for approval which can also imbibe into a teacher's perception sub-consciously and those can be related or can influenced the daily classroom teaching in the school.

Natrajan, S (1988) in her thesis work explored the need motivation of student learners. Her objectives were to study the relationship between the four need motivation: n-Achievement, n-Affiliation, n-Power and n-Approval and to study the nature of the above mentioned four levels of student learners on various backgrounds in the Chhattisgarh region. She found there was no significant territorial variation on either of the four need motivation as well as authoritarianism between the four levels of student learners. A significant difference between graduate and post-graduate students was observed on n-Ach.

Ramchandran (2005) had studied on the teacher's motivation in India. The study found out that at primary level due to low salary the teachers were often away from school on private business. It was also due to only two teachers and lots of children at the primary level, so they faced difficulty and became not interested to teach.

Suman et. al. (2007) investigated the level of achievement motive, anxiety and power motive among scheduled caste (Bantar, Musahar, Paswan & Ram) subjects. The results revealed that all the four caste groups did not differ significantly on achievement motive and anxiety. But a significant difference was found in between Bantar & Ram and Musahar & Ram in respect of power motive.

Gupta & Gehlawat (2013) studied job satisfaction and motivation of secondary school teachers in relation to demographic variables. The findings of the study shows that there were no significant difference in the motivation of male and female teachers, teachers working in private schools possessed significantly higher motivation than those working in government schools, less experienced teachers possessed significantly higher motivation than the more experienced teachers. The secondary school teachers' motivation and job satisfaction positively correlated.

Singh (2014) conducted a research to find out the effects of gender and types of parents on social motives. All the individualistic effects of achievement, power, affiliation and approval motives under social motives were studied. The differences were also observed for variables of gender and types of parents. It was found that, a) the male students have significantly high achievement motivation, power motivation, while the female students have significantly high affiliation motivation; b) There is no significant difference of approval motivation between male and female students, c) The double parents related students have significantly high power motivation, while the single parents students have significantly high approval motivation, d) The gender (male & female) significantly affect the achievement motivation, power motivation and affiliation motivation, e) The types of parents (single & double) also significantly affect the power motivation, approval motivation and achievement motivation and f) The interaction effect of gender (male & female) and types of parents (single & double) significantly affect the affiliation motivation. But the interaction effects of gender and types of parents do not significantly affect the achievement, power and approval motivation.

RESEARCH QUESTION

What is the status of Social Motives perceived by the secondary school teachers of West Bengal?

RESEARCH OBJECTIVE

To study the status of Social Motives perceived by the secondary school teachers of West Bengal

METHODOLOGY

The investigation was reductionist in nature. The study employed a survey design in which surveys were conducted by the present researcher personally to collect all the data from the respondent teachers. The population of the study was all secondary school teachers of West Bengal, teaching in the secondary schools under control of West Bengal Board of Secondary Education (WBBSE). 13 districts of West Bengal were randomly selected and from there 72 secondary schools and thereafter 7 teachers were selected randomly from each of the school. A total of 382 teachers were surveyed under this investigation. In measuring Social Motives of the secondary school teachers, the standardized scale, Social Motive Scale (SMS), by Dr. Singh and Dr. Pandey (2010) was adapted and used. To attain this objective, percentiles were calculated to identify and to categorize the status of social motives, perceived by secondary school teachers. In addition of this the four different dimensions of social motives, namely achievement motives, power motives, affiliation motives and approval motives were also calculated to identify and to categorize their statuses separately for the secondary school teachers. On the basis of the percentile, the scores were divided into three categories. The scores of above 75th percentile were considered to have high level and below 25th percentile were considered to have low level and in between 25th percentile to 75th percentile scores were considered to have moderate level.

FINDINGS

Among many dimensions of social motives, in this study, as four motives were taken into consideration viz. achievement motives, power motives, affiliation motive and approval motives, so the findings are also segmented in these four dimensions first and then in overall Social Motives. The status of secondary school teachers regarding Achievement Motives of Social Motives followed positively skewed trends.

Table 1: Percentile Status of the Achievement Motives for Secondary School Teachers				
Percentiles	Raw Scores	Levels of Achievement Motives	No. of Teachers	Percentage
Above P ₇₅	23& Above	High	110	28.79
P ₂₅ toP ₇₅	21 to 22	Moderate	125	32.73
Below P ₂₅	20& Below	Low	147	38.48
Total			382	100

The status of secondary school teachers regarding Power Motives of Social Motives followed normal trends.

Table 2: Percentile Status of the Power Motives for Secondary School Teachers				
Percentiles	Raw Scores	Levels of Power Motives	No. of Teachers	Percentage
Above P ₇₅	19& Above	High	123	32.19
P ₂₅ toP ₇₅	16 to 18	Moderate	147	38.48
Below P ₂₅	15& Below	Low	112	29.33
Total			382	100

The status of secondary school teachers regarding Affiliation Motives of Social Motives followed negatively skewed trends.

Table 3: Percentile Status of the Affiliation Motives for Secondary School Teachers

Percentiles	Raw Scores	Levels of Affiliation Motives	No. of Teachers	Percentage
Above P ₇₅	21& Above	High	141	36.91
P ₂₅ toP ₇₅	19 to 20	Moderate	128	33.51
Below P ₂₅	18& Below	Low	113	29.58
Total			382	100

The status of secondary school teachers regarding Approval Motives of Social Motives followed normal trends.

Table 4: Percentile Status of the Approval Motives for Secondary School Teachers

Percentiles	Raw Scores	Levels of Approval Motives	No. of Teachers	Percentage
Above P ₇₅	21& Above	High	109	28.53
P ₂₅ toP ₇₅	18 to 20	Moderate	166	43.45
Below P ₂₅	17& Below	Low	107	28.02
Total			382	100

The status of secondary school teachers regarding Social Motives collectively followed normal trends.

Table 5: Percentile Status of the Social Motives for Secondary School Teachers

Percentiles	Raw Scores	Levels of Social Motives	No. of Teachers	Percentage
Above P ₇₅	81& Above	High	103	26.97
P ₂₅ toP ₇₅	74 to 80	Moderate	166	43.45
Below P ₂₅	73& Below	Low	113	29.58
Total			382	100

DISCUSSION

The present researcher studied the overall status of social motives along with the statuses of its four dimensions separately namely Achievement Motives, Power Motives, Affiliation Motives and Power Motives also. In case of achievement motives, it was revealed that only 29% (110 in numbers) of the teachers were highly motivated in their achievement attribute, which was reasonably squat compare with the moderately motivated teachers of 33% (125 in numbers) and low motivated teachers of 38% (147 in numbers). Here maximum numbers (147) of teachers were of low achievement motivated behaviour. The teachers in their power motives showed a mixed trend where 32% (123 in numbers) of the teachers were of high level and 38% (147 in numbers) were of moderate level and 29% (112 in numbers) of them were of low level of power motives. Though the power motives is very frequent for the profession of teaching, but in the present socio-economic-legal context, it is still alarming that 29% of the teachers were of that sprain, if they have been exhibiting this mannerism into their classroom teaching or daily classroom situation regularly. As for affiliation motives is concerned, 37% (141 in numbers) of the teachers were highly motivated where 34% (128 in numbers) and 30% (113 in numbers) of the teachers were of moderately and low motivated respectively. It was quite a good sign that 71% of the sampled teachers were of more that moderately motivated in affiliation context, which should be rife for any teacher, teaching especially in upper-primary and secondary section. The approval motives had showed quite a customary trend where 28% for each in high level (109 in numbers) and in low level (107 in numbers) were recorded and 43% (166 in numbers) were recorded in moderate level. In case of approval motives, especially for the secondary school teachers, it was quite satisfactory in nature and was also anticipated. The overall status of Social Motives showed that 27% of the teachers were highly socially motivated getting score of above 81 in the prescribed tool, comprising of 103 secondary school teachers out of 382 sampled teachers. At the same time, it was also revealed that 30% of the teachers belong to the group of low socially motivated teachers, comprising of 113 secondary school teachers and 43% of the teachers were moderately motivated in societal context, comprising of 166 secondary school teachers. It focuses that the major portion (73%) of the teachers were motivated by the level of above moderate level in the societal context.

CONCLUSION

In Tolman's (1958) book, 'Behavior and Physiological Man', it is observed that Motivation is the willingness to do something and is continued by this action's ability to satisfy some needs for the individual. Well-motivated people are those with clearly defined goals who take action which they expect will achieve those goals. In other words motivation is a management function that stimulates individuals to accomplish laid down institutional goals. The findings of the study may be useful for different stakeholders of education like teacher educators, teachers, psychologists, educational planners, policy makers and schools. Secondary school teachers can be aware of such factors which may lead to increase achievement motives, power motives, affiliation motives and approval motives. The findings can also be helpful to the secondary school teachers in helping them for making better of their career and life goals.

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